

Appendix A

Results of pre-study I & II

Table A1

Results of pre-study I

Scenario	Scenario number	High		Low		<i>t</i> (9)	<i>p</i>	95% CI		Cohen's <i>d</i>
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	
Waste	1; 11	6.20	1.01	3.25	1.11	6.00	< .001***	1.84	4.06	1.90
Winter	2; 11	5.75	0.98	2.50	1.00	7.80	< .001***	2.31	4.19	2.47
School	3; 10	6.35	0.63	1.25	0.35	19.92	< .001***	4.52	5.68	6.30
Speed camera	4; 14	5.75	1.09	2.75	1.70	5.53	< .001***	1.77	4.23	1.75
Storm	5; 17	6.45	0.55	2.45	1.79	7.30	< .001***	2.76	5.24	2.31
Swimming	6; 15	6.05	0.86	1.85	1.31	10.25	< .001***	3.27	5.13	3.24
Ticket	7; 18	6.20	1.06	2.40	0.91	8.85	< .001***	2.83	4.77	2.80
City Park	8; 16	6.40	0.46	2.15	1.36	8.48	< .001***	3.12	5.38	2.68
City office	9; 12	5.55	1.19	2.60	1.52	5.75	< .001***	1.79	4.11	1.82

Note. $N = 10$. The comparison between the effect of high and low crisis responsibility crisis scenarios on attributed crisis responsibility is presented. The scenario number refers to the numbers used in appendix A. A seven-point rating scale was used. High = high crisis responsibility; Low = low crisis responsibility; CI = confidence interval; *LL* = lower limit; *UL* = upper limit.

*** $p < .001$.

Table A2*Results of pre-study II*

Scenario	Comparison	Tweet number	rational framing		humorous framing		$t(12) / Z$	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
			M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Waste	1	1; 10	1.15	0.28	3.98	1.86	5.72	< .001***	1.75	3.90	1.59
	2	1; 19			2.54	1.35	78	.002**	0.62	2.50	1.02
	3	1; 25			3.79	1.75	5.50	< .001***	1.59	3.68	1.52
	4	1; 27			2.81	1.72	91	.002**	0.75	3.00	0.93
	5	1; 32			3.46	1.70	4.56	< .001***	1.20	3.41	1.26
Winter	1	2; 11	1.40	0.71	3.44	1.48	4.43	< .001***	1.03	3.04	1.23
	2	11; 16			5.13	1.25	10.07	< .001***	2.92	4.54	2.79
	3	11; 28			4.29	1.65	7.58	< .001***	2.06	3.71	2.10
School	1	3; 13	1.12	0.24	4.32	1.59	7.34	< .001***	2.26	4.16	2.04
	2	13; 20			4.21	1.52	7.08	< .001***	2.14	4.05	1.96
Speed camera	1	4; 12	1.23	0.41	3.52	1.28	5.81	< .001***	1.43	3.15	1.61
	2	4; 21			5.12	1.13	12.24	< .001***	3.19	4.58	3.40
	3	4; 29			4.54	1.78	6.94	< .001***	2.27	4.35	1.93
Storm	1	5; 15	1.10	0.16	4.85	1.70	7.74	< .001***	2.69	4.81	2.15
	2	15; 22			4.27	1.66	6.53	< .001***	2.11	4.23	1.81
Swimming	1	6; 17	1.06	0.15	4.37	1.55	7.60	< .001***	2.36	4.26	2.11
	2	17; 31			4.13	1.55	6.95	< .001***	2.11	4.04	1.93
Ticket	1	7; 23	1.67	1.02	4.98	1.51	7.08	< .001***	2.29	4.33	1.96
City park	1	8; 18	1.04	0.09	3.94	1.71	5.97	< .001***	1.84	3.96	1.66
	2	18; 24			3.58	1.55	5.99	< .001***	1.58	3.50	1.60
City office	1	9; 14	1.08	0.16	4.77	1.67	8.35	< .001***	2.73	4.66	2.32

Scenario	Comparison	Tweet number	rational framing		humorous framing		$t(12) / Z$	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
			M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
	2	9; 26			3.71	1.74	5.66	< .001***	1.62	3.65	1.60
	3	9; 30			3.08	1.51	4.69	< .001***	1.07	2.93	1.30

Note. $N = 13$. The comparison between the effect of humorously and rationally framed tweets on perceived humor is presented. The tweet number refers to the numbers used in appendix B. CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit. If the differences of pairs did not follow a normal distribution, the paired samples Wilcoxon signed-rank test instead of the dependent sample t -test was used. The descriptive statistics for the rational framing are only printed once for each scenario. The tweets selected for the final study are printed in bold.

** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.